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DR. GUILBERT NICANOR A. ATILLO
Associate Professor V
Negros Oriental State University
guilbertnicanor.atillo@norsu.edu.ph

“MY JANITOR FISH”

I have a fish who loves to clean,
He keeps my fish tank nice and green.
He doesn't jump, he doesn't splash,
He just slides by in a quiet dash.

He sucks the glass and eats the dirt,
He never stops, he doesn't hurt.
He's not too fast, he's not too slow,
But he works hard, that I know!

He hides in rocks or stays so still,
Then cleans again—he's got the will!
No need for soap, no need to wish,
I'm proud of him—my janitor fish!